

ISic1070

I.Sicily inscription 1070

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (local)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Ispica

Provenance

From Grotta della Signora, nr. Molino

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140550

1. Σόσιος Βυχχύλος
2. διάκων ἐνθάδε
3. κῆτε· ἀνεπαύσετο
4. μηνὶ Νοβενβρίῳ
5. κ (αὶ)
6. ἀπὸ καλανδῶν γ'.
7. Ἄντ (ωνεΐα) Εὐφ ρ, ρ, σ [ύ]-
8. νη ἀνεπαύ [σα] τ (ο)
9. τῆ πρ, ὀ ια' κ (αλανδῶν) Δ, ξεκεν, β(ρίων).
- 10.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492697

EDCS 39102225

PHI 140550

Bibliography

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